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Research Article

RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for The Estimation of Citalopram in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Citalopram was estimated in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations using a reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method that was developed and validated in this work. Several technique factors, including buffer concentration, mobile phase ratio, and column type, were varied in statistically planned trials to evaluate the impact of these parameters on the chromatographic separation of citalopram. Methanol: Acetonitrile: Potassium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate buffer pH 4.5 in a ratio of 50:40:10 (v/v) was used to perform the separation on an Agilent Eclipse XDB C18 Column (250 x 4.6 mm and 5 μ m) at room temperature under isocratic conditions at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. A UV detector operating at 245 nm for a total of 8 minutes made the detection. In the concentration range of 10–35 μ g/mL, calibration curves were linear. The developed method's sensitivity is demonstrated by the observed LOD of 1.213 μ g/mL and the calculated LOQ of 3.129 μ g/mL. The method's robustness and ruggedness were confirmed by the %RSD being less than 2. In formulation analysis, the assay percentage was 98.95. As a result, citalopram in pharmaceutical formulations and bulk drug was routinely analysed using this technology

INTRODUCTION

Citalopram is a medication used to treat depression. Citalopram hydrobromide increases

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serotonergic activity in the central nervous system to produce its antidepressant effects. Citalopram hydrobromide has been shown in numerous trials to be a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) with negligible effects on dopamine and norepinephrine neuronal reuptake. [1-3] Citalopram is chemically (RS)-1-[3-(Di methylamino) propyl]-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-1,3-dihydroisobenzofuran-5-carbonitrile.

The chemical structure of Citalopram is [4,5]

R)-(-)-citalopram (top),
S)-(+)-citalopram (bottom)

Figure 1: Chemical Structure of Citalopram

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

Citalopram, the working standard medication, was acquired from MSN Laboratories Pvt Ltd in Hyderabad, Telangana. The local pharmacy provided the formulation dose form citalopram 80. We bought HPLC-grade acetonitrile, water, and methanol from Merck Chemicals Private Limited in Mumbai. The AR Grade buffer solutions used in the study were acquired from Merck Specialities Private Limited in Mumbai, India.

Preparation of standard drug solution

20 mg of the bulk medication Citalopram should be precisely weighed before being put into a 20 ml volumetric flask. To ensure that the medicine is completely dissolved in the diluent, add 10 ml of it and sonicate for 15 minutes. Now add diluent to bring the volume up to 20 ml. The solution has a 1000µg/ml concentration. To obtain a 100µg/ml solution, take 1 ml of this solution and dilute it to 10 ml. A working standard solution of 20µg/ml is obtained by diluting 1 ml of this solution to 10 ml.

Preparation of formulation solution

A clean, dry mortar and pestle were used to grind 10 Citalopram 20 tablets, each containing 20 mg of citalopram, to a fine, consistent powder. An airtight 20 mL volumetric flask was filled with a precisely weighed tablet powder containing 20 mg of citalopram. 10 mL of diluent was used to dissolve the tablet powder, resulting in a final volume of 20 ml. In the described method, formulation analysis was conducted using the same solution. Take 1 ml of this solution and dilute it in a 10 ml volumetric flask to make 10 ml. Take 1 ml of this solution and dilute it in a 10 ml volumetric flask to make 10 ml. The formulation analysis is conducted using this solution.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Selection of Wavelength

A standard solution of 10 µg/mL was made and scanned in a UV detector between 200 and 400 nm in order to choose an appropriate wavelength. The maximum wavelength that was acquired was chosen as the ideal wavelength for the detection.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Parameter	Condition
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Potassium Dihydrogen Ortho

	phosphate buffer pH 4.5 in the ratio of 50:40:10 (v/v)
Column	Agilent Eclipse XDB C18 Column (250 x 4.6 mm and 5µm)
Flow Rate	1.0 ml/min
Wavelength	245nm
Injection Volume	10 µL
Temperature	Ambient
Run time	8min

In accordance with the ICH requirements, the method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, LOD & LOQ, and system appropriateness. Replica injections of the sample and standard solutions into the column were used to conduct validation investigations. [6]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method Development

Selection of Wavelength

METHOD VALIDATION

Figure 2: UV Spectra of Citalopram

Table 1: Results for Optimized Chromatogram

S.NO	Drug	Retention Time (min)	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
1	Citalopram	4.325	4635	1.16

Figure 3: Optimized Chromatogram of Citalopram

METHOD VALIDATION

System suitability

Figure 4: Chromatogram of Blank

LOD & LOQ

Citalopram's LOD was found to be 1.213µg/mL, while its LOQ was determined to be 3.129µg/mL. The method's sensitivity and potential utility for drug detection and analysis at extremely low concentrations were validated by the results.

Linearity

The concentration range of 10–35 µg/mL showed linearity, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9998.

Table 2: Results for Linearity

S. No	Level	Seratrodast	
		Concentration in µg/mL	Peak Area
1	Level 1	10	128854
2	Level 2	15	228679
3	Level 3	20	319872
4	Level 4	25	420759
5	Level 5	30	531476
6	Level 6	35	639873

Figure 5: Linearity graph for Citalopram

Precision

Citalopram's percentage RSD was determined to be 0.42 for intraday precision and 0.45 for interday precision. For both intraday and interday

precision, the percentage RSD was found to be within the acceptable level of less than 2. Thus, it was discovered that the developed procedure was accurate.

Table 3: Results for Intraday Precision

S.No	Injection	Retention Time	Peak Area
1	Injection-1	4.295	1807534
2	Injection-2	4.286	1808186
3	Injection-3	4.317	1799832
4	Injection-4	4.325	1818820
5	Injection-5	4.309	1817984
6	Injection-6	4.322	1816998
Mean		4.309	1811559
STD		0.015582	7598.497
%RSD		0.35	0.42

Table 4: Results for Interday Precision

S.No	Injection	Retention Time	Peak Area
1	Injection-1	4.285	1808169
2	Injection-2	4.317	1799828
3	Injection-3	4.309	1816876
4	Injection-4	4.325	1818820
5	Injection-5	4.298	1807582
6	Injection-6	4.312	1799624
Mean		4.307667	1808483
STD		0.01425	8143.676
%RSD		0.33	0.45

Accuracy

The recovery percentage was found to be between 98.10 and 98.95%. At 50%, 100%, and 150% spiking levels, the percentage RSD was found to

be within the permissible range for Citalopram. The results showed that the suggested approach was accurate, with a % RSD of less than two and an acceptability limit of 98-102.

Table 5: Accuracy results for Citalopram

% Recovery	Concentration in µg/ml			Amount Found	% Recovery	% RSD
	Target	Spiked	Total			
50%	10	05	15	14.84	98.93	0.27
	10	05	15	14.89	99.26	
	10	05	15	14.92	99.46	
100%	10	10	20	19.75	98.75	0.28
	10	10	20	19.79	98.95	
	10	10	20	19.68	98.40	
150%	10	20	30	29.46	98.20	0.19
	10	20	30	29.54	98.46	
	10	20	30	29.43	98.10	

Ruggedness

The percentage RSD used to express ruggedness had to be less than 2. Citalopram's percentage RSD in the developed technique was 0.45. The method's robustness is confirmed by results that fall within the acceptable range.

Robustness

The percentage change for Citalopram in the developed technique was found to be within the permissible level of less than 2. As a consequence, the suggested approach was determined to be

appropriate for the analysis of Citalopram when there was a slight alteration in the analytical conditions. This confirms that a slight change in the analytical conditions has no effect on the results.

Assay

Citalopram's assay percentage in formulation analysis was 98.95%. As a result, the technique was determined to be appropriate for the regular examination of Citalopram in both formulations and bulk drug.

Figure 6: Chromatogram of Formulation

Table 6: Results for Formulation

S. No	Drug	Brand	Label Claim	Amount Found	% Assay
1	Citalopram	Citopam-20	20 mg	19.79mg	98.95

CONCLUSION

There were few data on the LC determination of citalopram in pharmaceutical formulations from the literature prior to the initiation of these research. A sensitive, accurate, and precise RP-HPLC method has been developed by the author for the measurement of citalopram in pharmaceutical formulations and in bulk pharmaceuticals. The recommended RP-HPLC technique for the citalopram test was shown to be

suitable for routine quantitative analysis following validation. The HPLC method saved time in preparing the standard and sample and did away with the requirement for time-consuming extraction. The low standard deviation statistics illustrate the exceptionally high precision of the developed method. The linearity, accuracy, specificity, and precision values were found to be within the acceptable ranges. The chromatogram's lack of extra peaks showed that the common excipients employed in the tablet did not conflict

with one another. Thus, it is shown that the devised RP-HPLC method is straightforward, linear, precise, sensitive, and repeatable. As a result, the devised approach is simple to use and has a fast analytical time for routine quality monitoring of citalopram in pharmaceutical formulations and bulk. The reported findings demonstrate the good accuracy and precision of the suggested approach.

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